

STUDY OF TRADITIONAL CLOTHES OF THE POPULATION OF UZBEKISTAN(in the example of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions)

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Abstract: Clothing is inextricably linked with the history of the Uzbek people, it is characterized by ethnic characteristics that reflect the national identity of peoples within the framework of material and cultural monuments. It is known that aspects characteristic of one ethnic group are expressed in clothing, and it is this aspect that serves to distinguish this ethnic group from other peoples, to differentiate it, to show its identity.

Key words: Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya, southern oasis, ethnos, traditional, material culture, tradition, ritual, national, clothing, jewelry, fabric, decoration, dress.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ТРАДИЦИОННОЙ ОДЕЖДЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА (на примере Кашкадарьинской и Сурхандарьинской областей)

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Аннотация: Одежда неразрывно связана с историей узбекского народа, для нее характерны этнические признаки, отражающие национальную самобытность народов в рамках материальных и культурных памятников. Известно, что в одежде выражаются аспекты, характерные для одного этноса, и именно этот аспект служит для того, чтобы отличить этот этнос от других народов, разграничить его, показать его самобытность.

Ключевые слова: Кашкадарья и Сурхандарья, южный оазис, этнос, традиционный, материальная культура, традиция, ритуал, национальный, одежда, украшения, ткань, украшение, платье.

ЎЗБЕКИСТОННИНГ АҲОЛИСИНИНГ АНЪАНАВИЙ КИЙИМ-КЕЧАКЛАРИНИНГ ЎРГАНИЛИШИ (Қашқадарё, Сурхондарё вилоятлари мисолида)

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Аннотация: Кийим-кечаклар ўзбек халқи тарихи билан узвий боғлиқ бўлиб, у моддий-маданий ёдгорликлар ичида халқларнинг миллий ўзига хослигини акс эттириб, этник белгилари билан ажралиб туради. Маълумки, кийимларда бирор-бир этносга хос жиҳатлар ифодаланади ва айнан шу жиҳат бу этносни бошқа халқлардан фарқлашга, чегаралашга, ўзлигини кўрсатишга хизмат қилади.

Калит сўзлар: Қашқадарё ва Сурхондарё, жанубий воҳа, этнос, анъанавий, моддий маданият, урф-одат, маросим, миллий, кийим – кечак, тақинчоқ, мато, безак, либос.

Through the study of clothes, it is possible to determine many socio-economic aspects typical of that period. The appearance of the camera in Turkestan in the 19th and 20th centuries was an important event, and a lot of evidence can be recovered based on these photographs. Photographer S. Dudin was the first to specially collect ethnographic collections on the peoples of Central Asia. From 1900 to 1908, he traveled around Turkestan almost every year and collected rich material from Shahrissabz and Kitab, among other cities. However, even before that, with the help of Turkestan governors-general, 32 All-Russian, Turkestan and world exhibitions were organized, under this pretext very unique items were selected for the imperial palaces and central museums. Such exhibitions were organized in 1869-1914. Of course, such gatherings were forced under the tutelage of Turkestan colonial authorities. In these exhibitions, a lot of space is reserved for the treasures of the Bukhara emir, and after the exhibition, all these rare items were sent to Moscow or Petersburg, to the imperial treasury or to the museum fund.

Although no comprehensive research was conducted during the Soviet period on the traditional clothes and jewelry of the inhabitants of the southern regions of Uzbekistan, general or fragmentary information specific to Central Asia was collected. For example, in some sources created in the 19th century, in particular, in the works of A. Vambéry, E. Meyendorff, A. Khoroskhin, A. Burns, N. Khanikov, etc., brief information about it can be found[1]. But in the early years of the Soviet era, new materials different from the previously known knowledge about it are hardly found.

In the 50s and 60s of the 20th century, a new era began in the study of the traditional clothes of the Uzbek people. In this place, it is possible to mention the researches of the scientist O. A. Sukhareva [2]. In the scientist's work "Voprosy izucheniya kostyuma Sredney Azii" information about the clothes of the peoples living in the region was collected, among which you can also find information about the clothes of the residents of the southern oasis [3]. His comments on headdresses,

outerwear, jewelry, the process of their preparation, fabric, design and other aspects are valuable and useful in comparative studies with respect to other periods.

In the work of H. Ismailov, information is given about the clothes of the Uzbek people, especially the southern oases, the types of fabrics used in their preparation, methods of preparation, design, jewelry, and clothing decorations [4]. At the same time, a separate chapter is devoted to this problem in the book entitled "Ethnograficheskie ocherki materialnoy kultury uzbekov", co-authored by academician K. Shoniyozov and H. Ismailov [5]. It should be noted that these works of the scientist were not written for the purpose of specifically studying the material culture of the inhabitants of the southern oasis. Nevertheless, the book contains valuable information about the ethnography of the inhabitants of the southern oases.

Material sources of clothing of the southern regions of Uzbekistan can be found in the collections of the Surkhondarya Regional Museum. These exhibits were collected in 1949-1955 during the scientific trip organized by V.S. Simonova and others to the city of Termiz.

Researchers M. Ibragimova and S. Davlatova specially studied the clothes and jewelry, various customs and rituals related to them [6]. In M. Ibragimova's work, the clothes and jewelry of the residents of Surkhondarya oasis, their cutting, sewing and preservation, as well as the customs and rituals related to men's, women's and children's clothes were researched. Notably, the work also provides interesting information about women's makeup training and makeup products.

S. Davlatova studied the changes in the national clothes of the Uzbeks of the Kashkadarya oasis in the late 19th and 20th centuries[7]. He emphasized that although women's traditional outerwear is distinguished by its unique decorations and patterns in each region and nation, they are distinguished by the same shape throughout Uzbekistan, i.e. straight, wide and long, and in different regions (Kashkadarya robe in Tashkent - peshwa, mursak; in Khorezm - misak; in Samarkand - munisak, kaltacha; in Fergana - munisak, munsak; in Bukhara - kaltacha) Using ethnographic, archeological and linguistic literature in the

framework of his scientific work, the researcher thoroughly explained the fabrics, manufacturing methods, jewelry and their classification, ceremonial clothes and related traditions and customs of the inhabitants of the Kashkadarya oasis. The fact that the researcher made a comparative analysis of different regions increased the importance of the work.

The work of the researcher N. Sodikova[8] also contains valuable information about the history of clothes of the southern oasis. In this work of the scientist, information is given about the history of Uzbek clothing, clothing fabrics, women's, men's and children's everyday and ceremonial clothes, their changes in accordance with the times. An important aspect of the book is that along with the information about the clothes of the inhabitants of the southern oasis, their pictorial illustrations are given. That is, the researcher was able to clearly show the condition of the clothes related to the oasis in the 20th century based on the field research materials.

S., who wrote a series of articles on the ethnic characteristics of the inhabitants of the Southern Surkhan oasis, the material and spiritual culture specific to the region, especially the costumes of the inhabitants of the oasis. and N. Tursunov's scientific research is noteworthy [9]. In their research, the clothes and used fabrics of the sedentary and herding inhabitants of the Southern Surkhan oasis, their similarities and differences were thoroughly analyzed.

In his research, Elshunos N.Tursunov provided information about the ceremonial costumes of the Southern Surkhan oasis based on field studies and written sources. Based on his ethnographic research, he points out that the traditional clothes, jewelry, ornaments, beliefs, and customs of various ethnic groups living in the region at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century were similar, had a common basis, or had a different appearance [10].

In the years of independence, ethnographic research of various regions of Uzbekistan reached a new level. Research has shifted from the general to the specific. Large area studies began to turn into small area studies. During the years of independence, I. Jabborov in his book on the ethnography of the Uzbek people

reports that there were many masters (chitgars) in Shahrissabz who gave various patterns to the yarn, and that the Shahrissabz hat was woven in a style similar to a multi-colored carpet, "like a ball of flowers". Elshunos devotes a special section of the book to studying the material culture of the Uzbek people. This section also provides valuable information about the traditional clothes and jewelry of the people of the southern oasis of Uzbekistan [11].

In the scientist's textbook "Fundamentals of the Ethnology of the Peoples of the World", a place has been allocated to the customs, economic style, and residences of the peoples of Central Asia, as well as their national clothes[12]. Of course, this information is given in a more general context, but is useful for comparative studies.

Elshunos A. Ashirov's monograph also contains information about ceremonial clothes and jewelry typical of the southern regions[13]. Based on the name of the monograph, this information is covered with an emphasis on ceremonial clothing, but ceremonial clothing is also an important symbol of the people's customs and traditions that have been preserved over the years. In this respect, the information presented in this monograph is valuable.

Academician K. Shoniyozov's works play an important role in studying the material and spiritual culture of the Uzbek people. For example, in the academician's monograph "The Karluq State and the Karluqs", information is given about the traditional occupation, agriculture and animal husbandry, handicrafts of the regions inhabited by the Karluqs, as well as about the clothes and jewelry of the inhabitants [14]. It can be seen from the content of the work that during the period of the Karagks, outerwear was mainly made of fabrics woven from woolen threads. The clothes of people of the upper class (khakan, khan, bek, etc.) were made of silk fabrics in most cases. Silk fabrics are brought to Movarounnahr from China via Eastern Turkestan. From this information, it can be understood that clothes have long been considered as one of the signs that show the different social classes of the population and divide them into levels.

In the book "Ethnograficheskie ocherki materialnoy kultury uzbekov" co-authored by Academician K. Shoniyozov and H. Ismailov, the clothes of the women of the Kashkadarya oasis are analyzed ethnographically. Based on the results of the analysis, oasis women's clothes are according to the seasons: winter, spring, summer, autumn clothes; according to the situation in which it is worn: everyday, festive and ceremonial clothes; according to which part of the body it is worn, it is noted that it is divided into: inner, upper, head and foot clothes.

In addition, it is worth noting that it is possible to determine the age, social status, and place in the family of women of the oasis by their clothes. According to experts, it was found out that women's clothes, although they look unchanged from the outside, but the shape and fabrics used for clothes have undergone serious changes. It can be mentioned that this condition was observed not only in the clothes of the women of the southern oasis, but also in the clothes of other regions of Uzbekistan.

In the book "O nekotorykh chertax regionalnoy obshchnosti v traditsionnom kostyme narodov Sredney Azii i Kazakhstan" by N. Lobachyova, women's costumes of the Kashkadarya oasis, like all Uzbek costumes, have been formed and developed over the centuries. He says that his interactions with the peoples had a certain effect. Such changes have left a deep impression on the general appearance of women's national dress (introduction of new elements) or on its various parts (fabric design, decorations). In general, as in the peoples of Central Asia at the beginning of the 20th century, the generality of women's clothes in the oasis is explained by their wide, long, straight shape and simple appearance [15].

The upper clothes of the inhabitants of the south are compact, cut to fit the body, and the waist is tied with a belt of leather or a special (yarn, mixed yarn) belt. The common people often wore outer clothes made of woolen fabrics, and tied their waists with a thinly woven woolen cord or chibchilgay (an edged woven item). In cold weather, a jacket made of woolen thread, a chaydam and a coat made of thin felt, warm trousers (dambal) made of tanned leather, etc. are worn. From these rates

reported by the researcher, it is clear that woolen and woolen yarn fabrics were leading in the clothing of the southern oasis of the 20th century. This situation has been formed over the years under the influence of the livestock-related lifestyle of the oasis residents. During the Soviet period, cotton fiber fabrics produced in factories also entered the region, but it is noteworthy that among the nomadic and semi-settled population, woolen clothes remained the leader.

Cases related to the wearing of clothes by the population in different situations have also been researched. For example, G. Tosheva, who studied the wedding ceremonies of the Uzbeks of the Kashkadarya oasis, provides information about the clothes and sarpo related to wedding ceremonies in her scientific work [16]. The information is descriptive in nature and is useful for comparative study with ceremonial clothes of other regions of Uzbekistan.

The book "Uzbeki" published in Russian also provides information on the clothes and jewelry of the inhabitants of the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya oases at the end of the 19th and 20th centuries based on photographs[16]. Since this information is mainly from sources collected during the Soviet period, it only summarizes the information provided by some of the researchers listed above. In order to write this book and fill it with new information, a special field expedition was not conducted in the territory of Uzbekistan.

It was found that the traditional clothes, jewelry, decorations, beliefs and rituals related to them of different ethnic groups in the region are similar to each other, have a common basis and have a unique appearance. In oasis-specific studies, the main attention was focused on folk crafts, traditional economy, clothes and customs related to them, and little attention was paid to the current situation of ethnic groups living in the research area, inter-ethnic processes between them, and transformational changes in material and spiritual life.

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